

THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL FOUNDATIONS OF FORMING A HEALTHY MINDSET IN PUPILS BASED ON THE COOPERATION OF THE FAMILY AND THE EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION

Shodieva Nodira Normamatovna

Teacher of TDPU named after Nizami

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Abstract. *This article discussed about the function of a family to form a person who is physically and psychologically healthy, spiritually mature, ready for work and family life, providing technology for forming healthy thinking in pupils based on the cooperation of family and educational institution, the cooperation of makhalla, educational institution and family in raising the young generation.*

Keywords: *family, cooperation, healthy thinking, technology.*

The analysis of scientific-pedagogical, psychological, physiological and philosophical works showed that the family and educational institution are the most important educational environment for a child, and in this environment, behavior, will, imagination, worldview and thinking important for the development of a person form and improve. The child sees the socio-spiritual image of the society in the image of the family, he understands the essence of the society's requirements in this small community. Family education has been highly valued in the East since time immemorial. Due to this, the role of the family in the formation of a mature generation cannot be denied, which is also reflected in our national values.

The role of objective and subjective factors in the development of a child as a well-rounded person in the family, and in the formation of healthy thinking in him is great. Objective factors include: the material support and well-being of the family, as well as the standard of living, the current state of the family budget, the experience of using it wisely, the stability of a healthy mental environment, etc.; the content of interpersonal relationships in the family, the physiological-psychological, cultural perfection and level of education of the family members, the balance between their interests and needs, reliance on the principles of unity, and so on are subjective factors. Correct organization of children's life in family upbringing means developing skills of purposeful and efficient use of time. So, the task of the family is to form a person who is physically and psychologically healthy, spiritually mature, ready for work and family life, for this purpose, the content of family education is to provide the directions of social education: physical, moral, mental, aesthetic, labor, ecological, economic, legal, political-ideological and sexual education, and to form skills and qualifications for independent activity in them.

Up to now, the prevention of negative consequences that may arise as a result of the changes taking place in the life of our country, the events taking place in the world community, their influence on the minds of young people, the way of people's behavior, it is necessary to form a healthy mindset in students. This, of course, requires a review of the capabilities and tasks of the family and the educational institution.

In order to manage the work of mutual cooperation, local coordinating public councils should be formed, consisting of makhalla activists, reputable parents, experienced employees of

educational institutions, and employees of various organizations located in makhalla. Based on the tasks undertaken by the public council, it can form small initiative groups within its structure that operate in different directions. It will be necessary for the community council to draw up a work program for a certain period of time, approve it at the community meeting, and implement it.

The mentioned events can consist of roundtable discussions, councils and meetings focused on a certain topic or problem, conferences, competitions, contests, meetings, and events dedicated to various dates that unite the people of the neighborhood and lead them to a healthy lifestyle. The established public council reports on its activities to the residents of makhalla once a quarter. When necessary, he listens to the reports of educational institutions, makhalla activists, organizations, enterprises and agencies located in the territory of makhalla on the educational work, providing them with practical and theoretical support has a positive influence on the effectiveness and consistency of the work. The council can apply various administrative measures in cooperation with state management agencies and human rights organizations against parents living in the territory of makhalla who are indifferent to the upbringing of their children. On the initiative of the council, extraordinary community gatherings, pedagogical councils of educational institutions or other necessary events can be organized on any relevant topic. The council coordinates work of schools, playgrounds, cultural centers, sports facilities, youth clubs, pre-school and out-of-school institutions in order to restore the traditions of Uzbek national education, hold various cultural events, and organize leisure activities for children and adults in the territory of the makhalla. The council analyzes the events, prepares methodological recommendations and covers these events in the media. In the education of young generation the Council ensures the cooperation of educational institutions, organizations and offices in makhalla in inclusion of the issues and problems related to cooperation of makhalla, educational institution and family in their work plans and practical programs. The establishment of these councils at the school, district, city and regional levels and the creation of an opportunity for council members to apply to all state and non-state organizations, foundations, community centers and various organizations within their competences, provides an opportunity to quickly implement the tasks of the council.

It is necessary to improve the management of state and public organizations in the process of continuous education in the formation of a healthy mindset in pupils based on the cooperation of the family and the educational institution, and to further expand the scope of their educational and upbringing influence. The formation of healthy thinking in pupils requires a clear material and moral basis in connection with the specific tasks facing this process. The basis of the education and upbringing process aimed at solving these tasks consist in planning, which requires modeling the expected results and methods of achieving them, the implementation of developed plans and models, and in this case, educational activity of the pedagogue related to the management of people's activities and behavior.

Based on the cooperation of family and educational institution, we used the materials of education and educational technologies that have been put into practice until now in the development of the technology of forming healthy thinking in pupils. To describe the technology, it is necessary to dwell on the expected result, the goal based on the result, and the clarified activity tasks.

Pedagogical tasks:

- formation of a motivational system in relation to learning activities among students;

- development of the ability to analytically analyze the events occurring in personal and social life, to express one's attitude firmly and to accept critical opinions;

- self-control, self-development and formation of a positive attitude towards oneself;

The expected result is to achieve a bright manifestation of a healthy way of thinking in pupils through the formation of theoretical and practical knowledge, skills and competencies related to the development of the human mind, the processes and laws of thinking.

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